

IMPLEMENTATION OF REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF PRE-SCHOOL AND SCHOOL EDUCATION AND FUTURE PRIORITIES

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Annotation: This article presents the views of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on improving the quality of education in preschool and school education and on important issues such as improving the quality of education at videoconferences created for teachers, introducing new methods, solving problems in kindergartens and schools, and training personnel. This videoconference discusses the attention paid by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the field of education, its achievements and shortcomings, and the procedure for including preschool children in preschool educational organizations.

Keywords: Educator, pupil, school, upbringing, coverage, child, education, pedagogue, activity, movement, individual, responsibility, reform, conditions, harmonious, individual, socio-economic, spiritual-educational radical reform.

In recent years, fundamental reforms have been carried out in the preschool education system in our Republic, and the Concept of Preschool Education, the “First Step” state curriculum, and a number of regulatory and legal frameworks have been created. It is worth recognizing that the attention and control of the head of state in the field of preschool education, and specifically the quality of education, is a positive result in the development of education and the improvement of the quality of education.

The organization of the upbringing of a harmonious personality has always been an important requirement and main goal of society. Naturally, in the conditions of current educational reforms, the upbringing of a harmonious personality is gaining importance. The socio-economic, spiritual and educational changes taking place at the current stage of society's development require a radical reform of the education sector, its complete liberation from ideological views and stereotypes left over from the past, the training of highly qualified, modern personnel who meet high spiritual and moral requirements at the level of developed democratic countries, and the improvement of the educational process.

Pedagogy is the responsibility of the “Preschool Education” direction of higher educational institutions. The rules of education are based on the upbringing of a complete person, based on the works of enlightened and thoughtful scientists of Central Asia and the world. Educators carry out education in preschool educational institutions. Every parent wants their child to receive education in the hands of a knowledgeable, highly skilled, and polite educator. The training of educators at the level of society’s demand is the responsibility of the “Preschool Education” direction of higher educational institutions. The rules of education are based on the upbringing of a complete person, based on the works of enlightened and thoughtful scientists of Central Asia and the world.

The requirements for preschool education are the content, methods, and forms of organization of educational work for children aged three to seven years in the family and in preschool educational organizations, and the preparation of children for school. Preschool education is based on theoretical and methodological foundations, the main focus is on the general foundations of preschool pedagogy, its scientific research methods, the content and methods of educating children of preschool age, ensuring consistency and continuity. When it comes to the

development of the preschool education sector and improving the quality of education, the following thoughts of the head of our state serve as a program to reveal the essence of the content of the article.

"The development of the economy, the future of our country and our children depend solely and exclusively on education and teachers. From the first day I started working with you, I have been saying: education, education, education, teachers, teachers, teachers." The development of education and upbringing, the improvement of the quality of education are aimed precisely at educators.

In particular; Many conditions have been created for creating suitable conditions for teachers, building and equipping kindergartens and schools, bringing in specialists from abroad, introducing modern textbooks and curricula, and this is being continued. Our President's words, "addressed to the leaders of kindergartens, schools, technical schools, and universities to which we entrust our children. Our economy must be strong for our people to live well! For this, we need new goods, new services, and new technologies! We can achieve this only through a quality education system! We have no other way! Realizing this truth, the leader who works hard every day will definitely see changes and results in his district, kindergarten, school, technical school, and university!" - these thoughts increase the attention of representatives of the industry to his profession.

Starting from September 2025, the salary of school principals, kindergarten directors and their deputies will also exceed 10 million soums. It is no secret that the result of the profession is reflected in the effectiveness and productivity of work through the appropriate assessment of the salary of the industry. "My words to our people that we will eventually bring the salary of teachers to a thousand dollars have become a reality in the past three years, which gives even more strength to industry specialists. In order to improve the potential of personnel and replace teachers with

secondary specialized education with specialists with higher education, a "1 + 5" (1 day of study, 5 days of work) bachelor's education form will be introduced in pedagogical universities for educators with secondary specialized education from the new academic year. Through this, about 10 thousand specialists with higher education will enter kindergartens every year.

Another noteworthy aspect is that from the new academic year, "Future Hour" classes are being held every Monday in all kindergartens, schools, and universities. One of the urgent tasks is to convey universal, national values, the idea of patriotism, and reforms in New Uzbekistan to children of the technological age in a deeper, more modern way in the changing times.

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